

Barometers of Change: The Silencing and Reintroduction of Organs during the English 'Long Reformation'

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The fate of church organs during the English Reformation is one of the tributary narratives which feeds into any account of the social, political and religious upheavals of the years between 1530 and 1660. Reformers in other parts of northern Europe had their own debates about the use of organs in worship. Lutherans willingly adopted organs to provide congregational accompaniments and introductory preludes to the singing of chorales, and they became increasingly important features of Lutheran services; Calvinists remained suspicious, but many town councils tolerated the retention of organs in churches if put to secular use. English reformers were more ambivalent. Organs became lightning conductors for outbreaks of destructive iconoclasm or (later) campaigns to restore a more 'ceremonious' style of worship. The latter, of course, culminated in the parliamentary prohibition of the use of organs in worship and led to the destruction of the vast majority of church organs in the 1640s. 'Barometers of change', indeed.

Any account of the provision, use and ubiquity of organs on the eve of the Reformation has to be qualified by the random survival of sources: churchwardens' accounts, inventories, visitation reports, and so on. The loss of monastic archives is particularly significant, because some of the most ambitious instruments were commissioned by monastic communities: Abbot Wheathampstede's two organs for St Alban's Abbey, one costing more than £17 in 1428, and the second costing more than £50 in 1438—reputed to be the largest and finest in any monastery in the kingdom—hint at histories that are now irrecoverable.¹ We fare better in the cathedral archives, of course. For example, in 1513 Exeter Cathedral commissioned what must surely have been an exceptional instrument for the pulpitum from an organ-builder named Laurence Playssher.² It cost more than £164 at a time when an organ for a major parish church was seldom more than £12 or £15. What proportion of parish churches were equipped with organs is difficult to establish; a recent (incomplete) survey of churchwardens' accounts in Kent found 52 parishes maintaining organs on the eve of the Reformation,³ but this is to take no account of places where records are lost. It may well be typical of other prosperous regions

¹ Frank Ll. Harrison, *Music in Medieval Britain* (republished, Buren: Frits Knuf, 1980), 211–12; Andrew Lucas, *The Organs and Musicians of St Albans Abbey* (St Albans: Friends of St Albans Abbey, 2009), 6.

² Malcolm Walker and David Davies, *Heavenly Harmony: Organs and Organists of Exeter Cathedral* (Exeter: Impress Books Ltd, 2014), 4–5.

³ Research by Joan Jeffery communicated to the writer (incomplete).

including East Anglia, and certainly typical of London.

Monastic churches, secular cathedrals and collegiate churches often had several instruments. On the eve of the Dissolution, Waltham Abbey had 'a lytell payre of organes' in the Lady Chapel, and in the choir, 'a great larg payre' and 'a lesser payre'.⁴ Durham, famously, had a hierarchy of three organs in the choir, used on occasions of differing solemnity, as well as other organs beside the Jesus altar in the nave and Our Lady's altar in the Gallilee chapel.⁵ The development of enriched polyphony offered new opportunities for the use of organs, and it is probably no coincidence that responsibility for playing the organ was progressively divorced from the singers, and given to a specialist.

The increasing use of organs in alternatim performance was not uncontroversial, nor was the elaboration of polyphony. Some of the religious orders, including the Carthusians and, to a lesser extent, the Cistercians, were resistant. But the break with Rome released more widespread objections. In 1536, a Protestation against 'faults and abuses' in religion was submitted to the Lower House of Convocation, including a declaration that 'the singing or saying of Masse, Mattens or Even-song, is but a roeing, howling, whistleing, mumming ... and juggling: and the playing at the Organs [is] a foolish vanity'.⁶ Fourteen years later, in February 1550, a first set of Royal Injunctions for St George's Chapel, Windsor, sounded a similar note:

... whereas heretofore, when descant, prick-song, and organs were too much used ... in the church, great search was made for cunning men in that faculty, among whom there were many that had joined with such cunning evil conditions, as pride, contention, railing, drunkenness, contempt of their superiors, or such-like vice; we now ... do enjoin that from henceforth when the room of any of the clerks shall be void ... the Dean shall make search for quiet and honest men, learned in the Latin tongue, which have competent voices and can sing ...⁷

In other words, organs and those who played them had got into bad company, and were consequently tainted by association. By October 1550, when the Windsor Injunctions were amplified and confirmed, it seems that the use of the organ had been discontinued, because provision was made for John Merbecke and George Thaxton, the organists, to receive their customary fees 'in as large and ample manner, as if organ playing had still continued in the Church'.⁸

It is around this time that there is evidence of a concerted effort on the part of at least some bishops, supported (no doubt) by Protector Northumberland, to silence organs in their cathedral churches. In 1552, Archbishop Robert Holgate made a visitation of York Minster. Two clauses of his subsequent injunctions concerned the organs and organist:

We will and commaunde that there be no more playnge of the orgaynes either at the Mornyng prayour, the Communion, or the Evenyng prayour within the

⁴Harrison, *Music in Medieval Britain*, 192–3.

⁵*Ibid.*, 187–9; *The Rites and Monuments of the Cathedral Church of Durham* (London: Surtees Society, 1844), 14.

⁶Thomas Fuller, *The Church-History of Britain* (London, 1655), 211.

⁷W.H. Frere and W.P.M. Kennedy, *Visitation Articles and Injunctions of the Reformation Period*, Alcuin Club Collections, XIV–XVI (1910), ii, 225.

⁸*Ibid.*, 258.

churche of Yorke, but that the said playnge do utterlie cease ...⁹

The second clause made provision for the displaced organist to receive a stipend for singing with the choir, as well as continuing to train the choristers.¹⁰

Holgate's attempt to silence the organs coincides with a similar order issued by the Bishop of London, Nicholas Ridley, to the Dean and Chapter of St Paul's. This was apparently under the direction of Cranmer who was conducting a visitation in Cambridge.¹¹ This could be evidence of a more general attempt by the reformers to silence organs at the end of Edward VI's reign. If so, it was all part of the more far-reaching attempt by the Protestant party to radically reform the performance and style of church music by adopting vernacular texts, drastically simplifying the musical style, introducing congregational psalm-singing, and disbanding or reforming choral foundations, including that at King's College, Cambridge in 1549.¹²

The Marian reaction of 1553–8 offered a brief respite, with some evidence of organs that had been alienated being restored (for example, at St Andrew's, Holborn, where the parish paid £5 in 1553 to recover their organ) and repaired (for example, in St Michael's, Cornhill, where Thomas Howe was paid 'for mendinge of the greate orgaynes and the small paire being broken, in the takeinge downe', in 1554). They also resumed their former place in the celebration of the Church's festivals: in 1555, Howe was paid for 'new cleansynge of all the pypes against Witsontyde' at St Mary, Woolnoth, and in the following year, he received 2 shillings 'for mendyng of bothe the payres of organs against the [As]umpcion of our Ladye' at St Mary-at-Hill.¹³ But this restoration was short-lived.

The advent of the Elizabethan regime in 1558 heralded a second dismantling of the apparatus of Catholic worship and the emergence of a new religious settlement which restored most of the provisions of the earlier Protestant settlement under Edward VI. Elizabeth, however, was too shrewd an operator to reveal her hand immediately, and she took the opportunity in the royal injunctions issued in the summer of 1559 to commend the use in collegiate and some parish churches of singing by choirs of men and children, stipulating the use of 'a modest distinct song, so used in all parts of the common prayers of the Church, that the same may be as plainly understood, as if it were read without singing', and also permitted that at the beginning or end of common prayers 'there may be sung an Hymn, or such like song, to the praise of Almighty God, in the best sort of melody and music that may be conveniently devised'.¹⁴ Nothing is said about the use of organs, but the practice of the Chapel Royal—which in the course of the reign became something of a template and source of repertoire for cathedrals and collegiate establishments—indicated quite unambiguously where the Queen's preferences lay, to the horror of the embryonic Puritan party. In 1562, a programme of reform was put before the Lower House of Convocation which included the abolition of 'all curious singing and playing of the organs'. It was defeated, but later in the year, a programme of reform including

⁹ [James Raine (ed.)], *The Statutes, etc. of the Cathedral Church of York* (London, 1879), 77.

¹⁰ *Idem*.

¹¹ Peter le Huray, *Music and the Reformation in England, 1549–1660* (Oxford: Oxford University Press, 1967), 26.

¹² *Ibid.*, 24–5.

¹³ Andrew Freeman, 'Records of British Organ-Builders', in *Dictionary of Organs and Organists* (London, 1921), 14–16.

¹⁴ le Huray, *Music and the Reformation in England*, 33.

a simple proposal ‘that the use of organs be removed’ was defeated by a single vote.¹⁵

The relative stability of the Elizabethan regime provides an opportunity to track developments in the deployment of choirs and organs over an extended period of forty-five years. The Puritans were arguably most vocal in their objections during the early years of the reign, culminating in the disastrous falling-out between the Queen and Archbishop Edmund Grindal over ‘prophesyings’ in 1577, leading to Grindal’s suspension. It was during this period that Bishop Sandys of Worcester ordered the demolishing of ‘a great pair of organs, which cost £200 [in] the making, being one of the most solemn instruments of this realm’ in his Cathedral; the pipes were allegedly ‘molten into dishes’ for the prebendaries wives, and the case made into bedsteads.¹⁶ Meanwhile at Norwich in 1570, the prebendaries broke up the organ which had then to be replaced in 1578 when the Queen paid a visit,¹⁷ and in 1571 Bishop Horne of Winchester issued injunctions to Winchester College, ordering that ‘the organs be no more used in service time, and the stipend for the organ player ... [be] turned to some other godly and necessary purpose’.¹⁸

Others of the Calvinist party were less opposed to the cultivation of church music. William Whittingham, the Calvinist Dean of Durham from 1563, was said to be ‘very carefull to provide the best songs and anthems that could be got out of the Queen’s chapel, to furnish the quire with all, himself being skillful in music’.¹⁹ A contemporary source confirms that one of the quire organs at Durham was played daily at services during the reigns of Elizabeth and James I.²⁰ The reference to Whittingham sourcing new repertoire from the Chapel Royal is, of course, very significant. During the Elizabethan years (and indeed later), the Chapel became a nursery for singers, composers and players who would pioneer settings of the new vernacular texts, and develop a style of performance to replace the elaborate polyphonic textures and alternatim practice of the pre-Reformation years. Without the Queen’s patronage and protection (for some of the most distinguished practitioners were, of course, closet Catholics) this would hardly have happened, and the great flowering of English choral music would (at best) have taken a different form. This was to have crucial consequences for the evolution of the organs built in the Jacobean and Caroline years.

The use of organs and other instruments in the royal chapel was interpreted as sanctioning their use in cathedrals and college chapels, and the records reveal that organs in many of these institutions were maintained, repaired and occasionally replaced during these years. There must have been much sucking of teeth in the Puritan camp when, in 1564-5, Archbishop Matthew Parker paid for a new organ in Canterbury Cathedral costing £56 4s 9d. Significantly, it was placed in a gallery on the north side of the quire where it was well-placed to accompany the singers – a location which was widely adopted in cathedrals. Regrettably, the organ was not a great success, but this did not stop the Dean and Chapter laying out a further £46 on its rebuilding ten years later.²¹ There was also a second pair of ‘little organs’ in the quire, which

¹⁵Huray, *Music and the Reformation in England*, 35–6.

¹⁶Jonathan Willis, *Church Music and Protestantism in Post-Reformation England* (Farnham: Ashgate, 2010), 141–2.

¹⁷Noel Boston, *The Musical History of Norwich Cathedral* (Norwich, 1963), 7.

¹⁸Willis, *Church Music and Protestantism*, 141.

¹⁹le Huray, *Music and the Reformation in England*, 39.

²⁰Harrison, *Music in Medieval Britain*, 213.

²¹Roger Bowers, ‘The Liturgy of the Cathedral and its Music’ in Patrick Collinson, et al. (eds), *A History of Canterbury Cathedral* (Oxford: Oxford University Press, 1995), 434–5.

Roger Bowers has conjectured was used to accompany anthems and services in the new verse style.²²

As for parish churches, the picture is far less clear, not least because of the patchy survival of records. We know of organs that were sold. At St Lawrence, Reading, for example, the 'lytell organs in St John's chauncell' remained until 1578, apparently unused, until it was agreed 'for that they should not be forfeited into the hands of the organ takers', they would be taken down and sold. The pipes were disposed of as scrap metal, and the wooden case was used to make seats for the mayor and aldermen.²³ An inventory of 1583 at Great St Mary's in Cambridge records 'an Orgaine Case with some pypes'; it was eventually disposed of for £1 in 1613–14.²⁴ Elsewhere, however, some parish organs were being used and maintained. In 1562, Henry Machyn reported that congregational psalm-singing at St Martin, Ludgate, was supported by 'the base of the organes',²⁵ and many years later in 1641, parishioners of St Wulfrum's, Grantham petitioned 'to have the organ continued and used in our church as it has been, viz. to accompany the singing of the psalms after the common and plain tunes appointed to be used in the church'.²⁶ That sounds like a long-established and valued custom.

Earlier historians have tended to assume, on limited evidence, that the disuse, and destruction or disposal of pre-Reformation parish organs was widespread during the Elizabethan period. No doubt there were regional variations, depending on the strength of local feeling, but more recent surveys by Jonathan Willis and Christopher Marsh have suggested that a significant number of organs were maintained and used, mainly (presumably) to support the new metrical psalmody.²⁷ Willis has also pointed to what he terms a 'skills vacuum' as contributing to the decline in the use of organs in London's churches. John Howe, the leading London organ-builder of the day, who seems to have maintained a 'virtual monopoly' in the City, died in 1571 and there may have been no one to replace him.²⁸ In other parts of the country, such as the south-west where the Chappington family was active, there is evidence of organs being maintained and new organs built – for example in the neighbouring and no doubt rival churches of St Edmund and St Thomas in Salisbury, where expensive organs each costing more than £35 were commissioned in, respectively, 1567 and 1569.²⁹ It must also be remembered that, even when organs were removed, it may have had as much to do with straitened parish finances as with religious radicalism.

I have said little so far about organs in the two universities. I will concentrate on Cambridge, partly because I have researched the archives of the various colleges more extensively, but also because the story that emerges neatly concludes the Elizabethan years and introduces us to the controversies of the next two reigns.

²² *Idem.*

²³ Andrew Freeman, 'A Short History of the Organs of the Church of St Lawrence at Reading', *The Organ* 1 (1921), 109.

²⁴ Nicholas Thistlethwaite, *The Organs of Cambridge* (2nd edn; Oxford: Positif Press, 2008), 115.

²⁵ John Gough Nichols, ed. *The Diary of Henry Machyn* (London: Camden Society, 1848), 228.

²⁶ Judith Maltby, *Prayer Book and People in Elizabethan and Early Stuart England* (Cambridge: Cambridge University Press, 1998), 3, fn.7.

²⁷ Willis, *Church Music and Protestantism*, 90–103; Christopher Marsh, *Music and Society in Early Modern England* (Cambridge: Cambridge University Press, 2010), 394–405.

²⁸ Willis, *Church Music and Protestantism*, 94–7.

²⁹ Freeman, *Records of British Organ-builders*, 33–4.

Cambridge, of course, was a stronghold of the Calvinist party for much of Elizabeth's reign. During those years, at least six colleges (Christ's, Jesus, Pembroke, Queens', Caius and St John's) removed organs from their chapels, and in 1570,³⁰ the royal commissioners led by Richard Cox, Bishop of Ely, ordered Roger Goad, the new Calvinist Provost of King's, to remove the organs from the college chapel.³¹

By the 1590s, the mood music had changed, and Cambridge witnessed the first serious assaults on the Calvinist position in a sermon before the University in 1595 by William Barrett, and lectures by Peter Baro and John Overall in 1596 and 1599, respectively. In 1593, Dr Thomas Nevile was appointed Master of Trinity College. He proceeded to re-establish the choral foundation and commissioned the repair, or possibly replacement, of the chapel organ.³² Four years later, Nevile became Dean of Canterbury and initiated a similar revival in the musical life of the Cathedral.³³ The Calvinist bishops and divines were no longer left unchallenged, and the ground was prepared for what became a proto-Arminian, and ultimately Laudian movement to restore 'the beauty of holiness' to the English Church in which music and organs would have a vital and legitimate place.

In the time remaining, we must focus on a few highlights of these developments. The commissioning of a new organ for King's College in 1605 was highly significant, not least because of the involvement of Robert Cecil, Chancellor of the University and the King's chief minister.³⁴ Provost Goad was still in post and was roundly condemned for failing to fulfil the requirements of the college statutes that an organ should be maintained. A new instrument was ordered from the organ-builder, Thomas Dallam. He and his son, Robert Dallam, were the principal beneficiaries of the movement to reintroduce organs which gathered pace over the next four decades, but we know little about their background. It is likely that the family came from Westmorland and were recusants, but where the elder Dallam learned his craft is unknown. He first appears in company with the Queen's clock-maker, Randolph Bull, delivering a large and elaborate mechanical organ-clock to the Sultan of Turkey in Constantinople in 1599.³⁵ It was a present from the Levant Company, on behalf of the Queen. Six years later he is in Cambridge, where he spends almost twelve months constructing the lavish new organ for King's at the cost of £371, about a third of which was to pay joiners, carvers and painters for the construction and embellishment of the case. The organ was installed at the east end of the chapel, probably on the platform where the pre-Reformation High Altar had stood. (The Elizabethan communion table was placed lengthwise between the stalls.) To any who were inclined to take offence at the use of organs in worship, this prominent position, coupled with the highly enriched case decoration, must have been a particular affront.

But perhaps most significantly, this was the first English organ that we know to have possessed two keyboards, the 'Greate Organ' and the 'Chayre Organ', the latter in its own case behind the player. This established the pattern for all the larger organs that the Dallams built over

³⁰Thistlethwaite, *Organs of Cambridge*, passim.

³¹*Ibid.*, 58.

³²Ian Payne, 'The Musical Establishment at Trinity College, Cambridge, 1546–1644', *Proceedings of the Cambridge Antiquarian Society* LXXIV (1985), 61.

³³Roger Bowers, 'The Liturgy of the Cathedral', in *History of Canterbury Cathedral*, 439–41.

³⁴For this account of the King's College organ, see, Nicholas Thistlethwaite, 'The Organ of King's College, Cambridge, 1605–1802', *BIOS Journal*, 32 (2008), 4–42.

³⁵Dominic Gwynn, 'Where did Thomas Dallam Learn how to Build Organs?', *BIOS Journal* 44 (2020), 10–20.

the next thirty years, including instruments for the cathedrals of Norwich (1608), Worcester (1613), Wells (1620), Durham (1621) and Bristol (1629), Magdalen College, Oxford (1631), York Minster (1634) and Gloucester Cathedral (1641).³⁶

The question, of course, is why this disposition was chosen. The stop-list of the King's organ has not survived, but that for the Worcester organ of 1613 has.³⁷ It includes an 8-stop Great Organ with duplicated open diapasons, principals and fifteenths, and a 5-stop Chaire Organ with a stopped diapason and principal, a flute of 4' pitch, a fifteenth and a two-and-twentieth. Was this designed to cater for the accompanimental needs of the new verse anthems and settings, the Chaire Organ introducing and accompanying the solo verses, and the Great Organ supporting the full choir sections? It seems possible, at least, especially as some of the Chaire Organs included a flute stop actually described as a register 'to sing to'.³⁸

In some instances, these 2-manual instruments were created by combining two existing organs. At Windsor in 1609, for example, Dallam was ordered to rebuild the two existing organs to create a 'whole Instrument Consistinge of a greate organ and a Chayre Portative'.³⁹ Roger Bowers conjectures that something similar happened at Canterbury in 1619,⁴⁰ while at Lichfield in 1634, following a visitation by Archbishop Laud, the Dean and Chapter were told to improve the 'organes', accompanied by advice 'that you putt them both into one, and make a chayre organ of them'.⁴¹ There is evidence that steps were also taken to upgrade the organs in the royal chapels by incorporating Chair Organs in this period. An order was issued in 1637, 'for altering and Raparacons of the Organ in our Chappell of Hampton Courte, and for the making of a newe Chaire Organ their conformable to those allreadie made in our Royall Chappell at Whitehall and Greenwich'. The organ at Richmond Palace was also rebuilt two years later, possibly with the same object in mind so that the choral service with its verse settings could be properly accompanied.⁴²

Meanwhile in Cambridge other colleges acquired organs as the masterships fell to Laud's allies. The appointments of Benjamin Laney to Pembroke and Edward Martin to Queens' in 1630, of Richard Sterne to Jesus and William Beale to St John's in 1634, and finally of John Cosin to Peterhouse in 1635 were all followed by the reform of liturgical arrangements, including the installation of organs. Peterhouse, in particular, became a focus of anti-Calvinist approbation and Puritan censure for its wholehearted embrace of the Laudian project. Cosin had already encountered bitter criticism from his adversaries in Durham where he was a prebendary through the patronage of Bishop Neile. Peter Smart, another prebendary of the old puritanical school, levelled charges in 1628 against Cosin for changes made to the Cathedral services, turning the Sacrament into 'a theatrical stage play', and encouraging the playing of 'a pair of gorgeous organs, which have cost at least £700' (unlikely) during the daily early morn-

³⁶Stephen Bicknell, *The History of the English Organ* (Cambridge: Cambridge University Press, 1996), 72–88. Bicknell's claim that Thomas Dallam was born near Warrington is now generally agreed to be mistaken.

³⁷*Ibid.*, 77–8.

³⁸York Minster, 1632–4; Lichfield Cathedral, 1639–40. See, Bicknell, *The History of the English Organ*, 85–7.

³⁹Sidney Campbell and W.L. Sumner, 'The Organs and Organists of St George's Chapel, Windsor', *The Organ* XLV (1966), 146–7.

⁴⁰Bowers, 'The Liturgy of the Cathedral', 441.

⁴¹*Idem*; also, Herbert Snow, 'The Organs of Lichfield Cathedral', *The Organ* XII (1932), 98.

⁴²Andrew Ashbee, *Records of English Court Music*, 3. 1625–1649 (1991), 94.

ing service.⁴³ At Peterhouse, Cosin went further, installing an organ in 1637, establishing a choral foundation to sing the daily services, and recruiting an organist (Thomas Wilson) from Durham to compile an extensive repertoire of anthems and settings which survive in the Peterhouse part-books. For his enemies, this was simply more fuel to the fire.⁴⁴ It is therefore hardly surprising that when civil war finally erupted in 1642, organs were prime targets for outraged Puritans and unruly Parliamentary soldiers. The records of the vandalism they caused have often been quoted. At Westminster, for example, they burned the altar, and then ‘brake downe the Organs, and pawned the pipes at several ale-houses for pots of ale’. At Exeter, they again pulled down the organs, ‘and taking two or three hundred pipes with them in a most scornful and contemptuous manner, went up and downe the streets piping with them’. At Chichester, they dashed the pipes with their pole-axes, ‘scoffingly saying, “Harke how the organs goe”’.⁴⁵ Cambridge fared a little better, the colleges having stirred themselves to remove their organs to safety, but few reappeared in 1660, Peterhouse vainly endeavouring to reclaim Dr Cosin’s organ which had meanwhile been sold to a London merchant.⁴⁶ And in case anyone was in any doubt about the fate of organs and organ-playing under the Parliamentary regime, the 1644 Ordinance of the Lords and Commons ordered ‘the speedy demolishing of all organs, images and all matters of superstitious monuments in all Cathedrals, and Collegiate or Parish-Churches and Chapels, throughout the kingdom of England and the Dominion of Wales, the better to accomplish the blessed reformation so happily begun ...’.⁴⁷

There is little reason to doubt that Parliament’s instruction was widely followed, even if not every region had an agent as effective as William Dowsing in East Anglia.⁴⁸ Robert Dallam fled to Brittany on the outbreak of war, and, no doubt trading on his Catholic allegiances, turned himself into a successful French organ-builder. Other craftsmen remained in England, keeping their heads down, and maintained organs and other keyboard instruments in domestic and secular contexts.

Then in May 1660 the King returned. The Chapel Royal was re-established, Charles having promised that he would maintain ‘the good old order of the church in which he had been bred’, and the Book of Common Prayer, the royal ceremonies, and the singers and organists were also reinstated, albeit with some Gallic polish. As early as Sunday 17 June 1660 Samuel Pepys could report that ‘This day the organs did begin to play at Whitehall before the King’. Two weeks later, Pepys attended the chapel, and recorded in his diary that it was ‘the first time that ever I remember to have heard the Organs and singing-men in Surplices in my life’.⁴⁹ Robert Dallam, accompanied by other members of his extended family hastened back from Brittany, and were full of business, making new organs for churches, cathedrals, college chapels and (increasingly) for wealthy parish churches. Once again, the organ proved itself a barometer of change.

⁴³le Huray, *Music and the Reformation*, 47–51.

⁴⁴Nicholas Thistlethwaite, ‘Peterhouse, Cambridge: The Documentation of a Lost Organ, 1635–1667’, *BIOS Journal*, 46 (2022), 6–37.

⁴⁵*Mercurius Rusticus; The Country’s Complaint recounting the Sadder Events of this Unparalleled Warr*, 1647.

⁴⁶Thistlethwaite, ‘Peterhouse, Cambridge’, 27–9.

⁴⁷Bicknell, *The History of the English Organ*, 90.

⁴⁸Trevor Cooper, ed., *The Journal of William Dowsing* (Woodbridge: Boydell Press, 2001).

⁴⁹Robert Latham, ed., *The Shorter Pepys* (London: Bell & Hyman Ltd, 1985), 55, 61.